

Influence of Individual Consideration on Organizational Performance on Private Universities in Nairobi County, Kenya

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ABSTRACT: Transformational leadership is a process in which leaders and followers help each other to advance to a higher level of morale and motivation, creating significant changes in the lives of people and organizations. The purpose of the study was to investigate the influence of individualized consideration style on organization performance in private universities in Nairobi City County, Kenya. The objective that guided the study was to: establish the influence of individualized consideration on organizational performance in private universities in Nairobi City County, Kenya. The study used Transformational Leadership Theory by Burns (1978) and the conceptual framework was based on the relationship between individualized consideration style and organizational performance. The sample comprised of 288 lecturers and 7 Deans of Academic Affairs of the chartered private universities. Questionnaires and interview guides were used to gather data. Validation of the questionnaires was through Cronbach's Alpha and the use of expert judgement. The coefficient value was 0.879 at alpha = 0.05. Data was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Regression analysis showed a strong relationship between individualized consideration and the performance of private universities. The results revealed a positive and significant relationship between individualized consideration ($\beta = .370$, $p < .05$). It was concluded that offering leadership support and advice, mentorship, career development and solving individual needs among their employees influences performance. The following recommendations were made: the management of private universities ought to offer leadership support and advice to their employees, as well as helping in solving the employees' needs as this is important in improving their performance. Furthermore, they should realize that in order to realize higher performance for their institutions they need to ensure that the leaders in the institutions act as both mentors and coaches for the employees and recognize their contributions to the organization. The Deans of Academic Affairs need to attend seminars and training in transformational leadership so that they can be well-versed in transformational leadership skills, responsibilities, and characteristics.

KEYWORDS: Individualized consideration, Leadership support, Mentorship, Organizational performance, Private universities, Transformational leadership.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to Chandan (2021), leadership is the art of influencing and inspiring subordinates to perform their duties willingly, competently and enthusiastically for achievement of group objectives. Similarly, leaders are seen as people that are capable of making changes in order to attain a high level of performance (Desky et al., 2020), they must be able to create visions, develop strategies, and use his power to influence their subordinates positively (Indrawan et al., 2020). In addition, leaders who possess these qualities are classified as "Transformational Leaders" (Desky et al., 2020). Leaders have the ability to equalize his future vision with that of his subordinates and heighten his subordinates' needs (Kadiyono et al., 2020). Transformational leadership is a process in which leaders and followers help each other to advance to a higher level of morale and motivation, creating significant changes in the lives of people and organizations (Burns, 1978).

Alatawi (2022) conceptualized transformational leadership as comprising four I's: idealized Influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration. Individual consideration. Chebon, Aruasa and Chirchir (2019) described individualized consideration refers to the transformational leader's emphasis on and attention to individual follower's needs for achievement, growth, and career development. The process includes providing new learning opportunities in a supportive climate that takes into account individual differences. The leader monitors the work of the followers, not in a controlling way, but to furnish useful feedback and guidance (Ogolla, 2020). Bass (1995) discussed individualized attention as occurring when a leader pays attention to the differences among followers and discovers what motivates each individual. He proposed that individualized attention allows leaders to become familiar with followers, enhances communication and improves information exchange.

In line with the demand for change in organizations, there is a significant role that the model of transformational leadership is playing in organizational performance because transformational leader can create vision in an environment which can motivate the employees to achieve results that exceeds expectations (Gelard et al., 2019; Birasnay et al., 2021). Yukl (2009) cited in Milelu (2019) suggested that transformational leadership could help in building the work groups and integrate individual towards achievement of organizational corporate goal. According to Ahmad et al. (2019), transformational leadership plays a very crucial role in an organization in the sense that, it brings about positive change in the followers; it enhances the motivation, morale and performance, and that its relevance and contribution to organizational performance cannot be undermined.

One way of examining individualized consideration is through the performance of the private universities. With 17 fully chartered private universities in Kenya and 7 in Nairobi City County, the higher education sector has registered growth, attributable to a host of factors, among them the growing demand for university education. Consequently, there has been a strain on public universities to handle the subsequent demand. The growth of Private University sector in Kenya has further been attributed to the fact that most of the private universities in the country are established and managed and/or affiliated with religious organizations with massive followings diminishing; as well as the diminishing opportunities available in public universities. Being profit making entities, fees in private universities are accordingly charged in conformity to market forces on the grounds of full cost recovery (Altbach et al., 2019).

A. Statement of the Problem

Private university education has experienced a crisis ranging from deteriorating quality, unsustainable financing, limited research, relevance, low staff morale, and insufficient facilities due to the kind of leadership being applied (Mbirithi, 2019). This has affected the teaching quality and painted the wrong picture to the public as far as quality teaching and performance of universities is concerned (Lumbasi, K'aol & Ouma, 2016). The future of the private universities in Kenya depends on how well the university's leadership responds to the challenges and thus one of the critical factors in assessing how these universities respond to these challenges is their style of leadership (Abagi, 2017). Effectively, Kenyan private universities must formulate strategies to attract larger student enrolment, collaborate with the private sector and development partners to be self-sufficient (Ogolla, Bolo & Muchemi, 2019; Wanzala, 2019).

Michieka (2017) observed that research into leadership in Kenya has little influence on leadership in higher education. It may create major gaps in terms of leadership in universities in Kenya. In transformational leadership, when a leader does not show individualized consideration, they were also not aware of the unique talents that each follower brings to the workplace, thus not supporting them in developing and demonstrating these key skills and behaviors (Mansour et al., 2017). Therefore, there is need to explore ways of addressing the above challenges through sound responses, to meet the best individualized consideration leadership style for universities to remain competitive and to maximum performance. Universities are forced to adopt modern strategies that ensure that these organizations achieve their strategic objectives.

In leadership, the private universities have made an effort to ensure that there is good leadership that will in the long run influence the performance of the universities (Gaiti & Kiiru, 2021). Significant changes have been undertaken, such as introducing performance contracting, performance ranking of private sector institutions based on agreed criteria, and devolving services (Milelu, 2019). In addition, Aondo (2020) revealed that they have formulated strategies at corporate, business and functional levels in their quest to improve performance and compete in the global market. These changes have been seen as a tool to improve accountability, transparency, efficiency, and effectiveness in delivering quality services and improving the efficient utilization of resources to improve overall performance. The null hypothesis of this study was: There is no significant relationship between individualized consideration and organizational performance in private universities in Nairobi City County, Kenya.

B. Purpose and Objective of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the influence of individualized consideration style on organization performance in private universities in Nairobi City County, Kenya. The objective that guided the study was to: establish the influence of individualized consideration on organizational performance in private universities in Nairobi City County, Kenya.

II. EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Silva and Mendis (2019) posited that in individualized consideration, leaders care and offer support to followers, providing opportunities for the followers to grow individually, as they act as mentors and coaches to become adeptly to realize organization

performance. Mwove (2023) citing Avolio and Bass (1995) stated that a “leader displays more frequent individualized consideration by showing general support for the efforts of followers”. Karamat (2018) holds similar views as he states that consideration style leaders show a high level of concern for people and are supportive of them. He explains that such leaders seek and accept suggestions from subordinates, consult with employees in advance on important matters, and criticize the work rather than the people. An individual consideration leader has the characteristics to act as a coach or mentor to followers by taking into account each individual’s needs and strengths to realise growth and achieve their potential (Prasad & Junni, 2021). Kao and Tsai (2019) argued that transformational leaders give special attention to growth and achievement of their teams individually. This behaviour is representative of leaders who give a supportive environment in which they listen to the individual needs of the workers.

The study by Najeeb (2019) examined the effects of individual consideration on organizational performance and revealed a positive relationship between the two variables. A study by Komakech et al. (2021) revealed that individual consideration had a positive and significant influence on employee performance. Mwaniki, Muhoho and Njoroge (2020) investigated the influence of individualized transformational leadership on organizational performance of selected sacco’s in Kiambu County and revealed that established that individualized consideration had a strong positive relationship and significant influence on performance of Sacco’s. Furthermore, a study by Ondari et al. (2018) showed that there was significant relationship between individualized consideration and organizational performance of state-owned corporations in Kenya. Research results by Kinara et al. (2023) indicated that there is a positive and significant influence of individualized consideration on organizational performance. The study made the conclusion that individualized consideration dimensions of the leader made remarkable influence to organizational performance of county governments in South Eastern Kenya Economic Bloc.

However, the findings disagree with Juma and Ndisya’s (2019) study which found that the relationship between individualized consideration and organizational performance was negatively correlated and statistically insignificant. In addition, a study by Kimengich, Ngeno and Kaptingei (2020) concluded that headteachers’ individual consideration does not have a statistically significant relationship with learners’ academic performance in primary schools in Kericho County. Tahir (2019) concluded that the individual consideration act of transformational leadership does not have significant effect on organizational performance.

III. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Transformational leadership theory which focuses on leadership behaviors influencing positive changes in its followers informed this study. According to transformational leadership theory, transformational leadership involves leaders exerting influence on followers to increase their commitment to organizational performance (Antonakis & House, 2019; Shikokoti, Okoth, Chepkonga, 2023). This is realized when the leader is able to influence followers to increase their performance by motivating them to transcend self-interest and increase their level of commitment to the task at hand. The followers’ performance is achieved through higher degrees of extra effort, effectiveness, and satisfaction (Bush, 2008; Bush, 2013).

Northouse (2014) emphasized that the admiration and respect that transformational leaders exhibit is entrenched through commitment to advance the interests of the individuals in the group they are leading. Thus, individualized consideration is a quality of a leader who extends personalized attention to the followers, in which case, the leader plays both coaching and mentoring roles. This quality is associated with transformational leaders (Bass & Riggio, 2006). Transformational leaders are more interested in how their followers progress and develop. They do this by being mentors and coaches. From Bass and Avolio’s argument, Kirkbride (2006) extends this view by asserting that individualized consideration is at the core of transformational style of leadership. He says this because, in life there exists nothing as influential as taking care of the needs of an individual first, before your own as a leader. It is like psychological loyalty buying of a person by another, whether s/he is acting on a leadership front, or not (Sarros, Cooper & Santora, 2012). Shadraconis (2013) explained that individualized consideration provides leaders with the opportunity to interact with employees in a more meaningful manner. Thus, such an atmosphere, personalized and mutual communication becomes key assets for the organization.

The theory argues that good leadership in organizations can result to organizational productivity. It is argued by the theory that leaders who serve as role models are likely to shape the behaviour of workers. Leaders who recognize and support workers to own the change process in any organization are likely to face minimal resistance from workers (Evangelos & Psomas, 2022). The theory argues that organizations which succeed in implementing new policies formulated are attributed to competitive practices such as employee motivation, technological integration in the system and ability of the leaders to challenge the status quo (Fotopoulos, Psomas &

Vouzas, 2020). The theory opines that transformative leaders in any competitive organization are always keen in rewarding behaviour rather than individuals (Choi & Eboch, 2019). Furthermore, the theory suggests that organizations that fail to navigate in the dynamic business environment are highly rigid to embrace transformational leadership (Bell & Omachonu, 2021). Based on this theory, this study sought to investigate the influence of individualized consideration style on organization performance in private universities in Nairobi City County, Kenya.

IV. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Orodho (2017) noted that the conceptual framework is a model or diagrammatic way of examining the variables under study. It shows how the independent variable, which is individualized consideration influences the dependent variable, which is, performance of private universities. Figure 1 shows the relationship between individualized consideration and private universities performance.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework showing the relationship between independent and dependent variable

Individualized consideration was measured using leadership support and advice, mentorship, career development and solving individual needs among their employees.

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

A research design is the entire methodological frame of the study (Cooper & Schindler, 2014). Descriptive survey was adopted in this study. Descriptive research design was appropriate for this study since it enabled the researcher to provide detailed summaries on relevant variables of the study (Orodho, Khateta & Mugiraneza, 2016). These variables are individualized consideration as the independent variable and performance of private universities as the dependent variable.

The sample comprised of 288 lecturers and 7 Deans of Academic Affairs of the chartered private universities. The study utilized simple random sampling and purposive sampling to draw the study's population.

B. Research Instruments

Questionnaires and interview guides were used to gather data from the lecturers and Deans of Academic affairs respectively. Creswell (2012) noted that questionnaire can collect a large amount of information reasonably quickly. The questionnaire method was preferred because of the large number of respondents targeted and the nature of the information sought (Kothari, 2013). Galletta (2013) asserted that the interview guide was flexible and provides more in-depth responses to the questions at hand. It also helped in triangulating the responses from the questionnaire

C. Pretesting of Research Instruments

Pilot study is a small-scale preliminary study aimed at evaluating the feasibility of a research project in terms of cost, time and tools. The findings of which are used to refine the research design prior to conducting the full-scale study (Hildebrand & Ott, 2011). The pilot study was the first step in understanding the influence of individualized consideration style on the performance of private universities in Nairobi County, Kenya. The pilot study enabled the researcher to check whether the items used are valid and reliable and correct misunderstanding, detect possible flaws in measurement procedures and in the operationalization of independent variables, check language level, to weed out/restructure unclear statements, determine time limits and clarify instructions and eliminate ambiguity at the right time (Lucas & Donnellan, 2012).

Validation of the questionnaires were through use of expert judgement. Cronbach's Alpha was used to establish the reliability of the study's instruments. The coefficient value was 0.891 at $\alpha = 0.05$. A scale is reliable if Cronbach's coefficient alpha is well above the threshold value of 0.7 and the acceptable minimum of 0.6 (Hair et al., 2006).

D. Data Collection Procedures

The researcher first obtained a transmittal letter from the University department offices and a permit from the National Commission for Science, Technology and Innovation (NACOSTI) to aid in getting authorization from the private universities to collect data from the respondents in the premises. Trained and qualified research assistants distributed the questionnaire. Participation was however on a voluntary basis. The research assistants interviewed the respondents face-to-face. However, where they were unavailable or busy, the research assistants used the drop and pick method. After a week, the researcher and research assistants collected the questionnaires for analysis and those that had not completed were reminded and given two more days upon which the rest were treated as non-response rates.

Thereafter, the researcher contacted the Deans of Academic Affairs to schedule a time and day for conducting the interview. They then visited their offices as agreed and interviewed them for about 15 minutes. The interview data was collected by note taking.

E. Data Analysis

Data collected from the completed questionnaires were analyzed using a SPSS. Thematic analysis was used to analyze qualitative data and presented in prose. Quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive statistics (percentages, frequencies, mean and standard deviation). In addition, correlation analysis and regression analysis were used to determine the relationship between the variables.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Questionnaire Return Rate

Data was collected from 217 out of 288 lecturers (80.2%) in private universities in Nairobi County, Kenya. The questionnaire was administered to lecturers and the interview guides to Deans of Academic Affairs. The researcher targeted at least 70% of each category to participate. A total of five Deans of Academic Affairs from the private universities in Nairobi County, Kenya responded. Table 1 shows the questionnaire and interview guide return rate.

Table 1. Research Instruments' Response Rate

Respondents	Returned	Not returned	% Return rate
Lecturers	231	57	80.2
Deans of Academic Affairs	5	2	71.4

Table 1 indicates that the response rate of the lecturers was 80.2 percent while that of the Deans of Academic Affairs was 71.4 percent. According to Best and Kahn (2011), in a population where the respondents are either widely scattered across a large geographical area or are difficult to access, at least 70% of the sample picked will respond.

B. Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Demographic results showed that majority of the lecturers in private universities in Kenya were male 125(57.6 percent) while 92(42.4 percent) were female. Demographic information of the Deans of Academic affairs was 4(80.0 percent) male and 1(20.0 percent) female. The results revealed that there was high gender disparity of the lecturers and Deans of Academic Affairs.

Concerning the age of the respondents, majority of the lecturers (55.4 percent) and Deans of Academic Affairs (60.0 percent) were aged 40-50 years giving an indication that they are of diverse age categories hence cordial interaction with the management leading to a clear understanding of the transformational leadership and how it affects the performance of the private universities.

Regarding education level of the respondents, majority of the lecturers have attained PhD level of education comprising of 52.5 percent while all the Deans of Academic Affairs (100.0 percent) have attained PhD. This showed that there were adequate academic qualifications that qualify the respondents suitable in their line of duties respectively that contribute to the performance of the private universities.

Majority of the lecturers have worked in the education sector for 4-6 years (34.1 percent) and Deans of Academic Affairs had worked in the education sector for more than 10 years (100.0 percent) implying that they have an understanding of how transformational leadership affects the performance of universities. Furthermore, regarding years worked in the university, the lecturers have worked in the university for 4-6 years comprising 39.6 percent of the total sampled population while Deans of Academic Affairs have worked in the university for more than 10 years comprising of 80.0 percent. The findings reveal that the respondents have been in the private universities for a longer period and thus have a clear picture of how performance of the private universities is influenced by the different aspects of transformational leadership. Therefore, they can be able to give their opinions on the current study.

C. Performance of the Private Universities

The lecturers were required to indicate the agreement level on performance of private universities in Kenya. The findings are presented in frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviations (SD).

Table 2. Performance of the Private Universities

	N	Mean	SD
Customer Satisfaction			
This institution has highly satisfied clients/students	231	4.13	.966
This institution enjoys a good public image	231	4.03	1.042
This institution retains existing students and manage to attract new ones	231	4.13	.933
Business Processes			
The operational efficiency of this institution has increased over the last three years	231	3.89	1.057
This institution is generally innovative	231	3.90	.964
Productivity of lecturers is much higher than the industry average	231	4.03	1.101
Employee Satisfaction			
The university’s top managers promote and support innovative ideas, experimentation and creative processes	231	4.10	1.156
Lecturers’ trust in leadership is high	231	4.14	1.060
In our institution, we often organize internal training of our lecturers	231	3.72	1.096
Enrolment			
The number of students enrolling in the university has increased in the last 5 years	231	4.20	.898
Enrolment of students affects the performance of this university	231	4.31	.832
Average Mean	231	4.05	1.009

Regarding customer satisfaction, this institution has highly satisfied clients/students had a mean of 4.33 and SD of .966. The institution retains existing students and manage to attract new ones had a mean of 4.13 and SD of .933. Regarding business processes of the university, productivity of lecturers is much higher than the industry average had the highest mean of 4.03 and SD of .964. The operational efficiency of this institution has increased over the last three years had a mean of 3.89 and SD of 1.057. This institution is generally innovative had a mean of 3.90 and SD of .964.

With respect to employee satisfaction, the university’s top managers promote and support innovative ideas, experimentation and creative processes had a mean of 4.10 and SD of 1.156. Lecturers’ trust in leadership is high had a mean of 4.124 and SD of 1.060. In the institution, they often organize internal training of their lecturers had a mean of 3.72 ad SD of 1.096. On enrollment, enrolment of students affects the performance of this university had the highest mean of 4.31 and SD of .832. The number of students enrolling in the university has increased in the last 5 years had a mean of 4.20 and SD of .898.

Overall, in performance of the private universities, the average mean was 4.04 and SD of 1.009. This means that majority of the lecturers agreed that customer satisfaction, business processes, employee satisfaction and enrolment are important factors of performance in the universities. These findings concur with Söderlind and Geschwind (2019) who explained that universities utilize diverse criteria for measuring performance. These include student enrollment figures, rankings, research accomplishments,

publications, grant acquisitions, graduation rates, and the reputation of their faculty members (Söderlind & Geschwind, 2019; Ortagus et al., 2020). Al Khajeh (2018) further added that customer retention, productivity, profitability, ability to become accustomed to the ever-varying environment, employee satisfaction, growth and social responsibility are used to measure performance. Other indicators include: effectiveness, efficiency, quality, and company image (Waiganjo, Mukulu & Kahiri, 2017).

1) Responses from Interviews

One of the Deans of Academic Affairs stated that

“We encourage employee satisfaction recognizing employees regularly and valuing them, supporting their mental health and providing better benefits to ensure they are content. We also offer competitive pay in line with industry standards and the present cost of living. This is important as employee satisfaction established whether the employees are satisfied or not as satisfied employees are happier workers which in turn means quality work and good performance.”

Another Dean noted that when an organization has high quality human capital, they perform better, and deliver higher and more consistent returns to stakeholders. The satisfied employees are also more likely to be creative and come up with breakthroughs that allow the university to grow and change positively with the changing market conditions and time.

The Deans of Affairs noted that they use both monetary and non-monetary incentives to motivate their employees. They noted that the monetary incentives include commissions and bonuses for the good work done. The non-monetary incentives include certificates, gift vouchers, trophies, letters of appreciation, promotions, participation in decision -making, training, representing the universities at public and training forums, financial rewards to motivate their employees, growth opportunities, and special assignments. One of the Deans of Academic Affairs stated that

“More often than not, attractive remuneration packages are offered to entice best talentsto a position, ensuring they perform at maximum efficacy, and retain talented employees within the organization while commission-based remuneration are extended to encourage employees to meet organizational targets.”

The Deans of Academic Affairs pointed out that they create a conducive working environment that involves good university culture, management styles and human resource policies such as reward management, talent management, performance management and human resource planning. This is because employees want to feel that their talents and skills enables them to develop in a certain organization through growth opportunities and the absence of this leads to poor performance and dissatisfaction.

The internal business processes in the university include quick customer service and responding to enquiries on time, financial management, customer relationship management, supply chain management, knowledge management, inventory management employee onboarding, capacity utilization using technology, and internal communication.

The financial returns/Assets challenge the organization faces were highlighted a high taxation that has made assets very expensive, high maintenance costs, and high cost of living leading to high cost of expenditures such as electricity and water bills increasing. Monitoring of cash flow has also become a challenge as there have been delayed customer payments, and seasonal variations in enrollment, sales and costs, tax compliance as well as debt management.

D. Individualized Consideration and Organizational Performance

The researcher sought to determine the influence of individualized consideration on performance of private universities in Kenya. Individualized consideration has characteristics that are helpful and can be copied by management and lecturers of private universities thus increasing performance. This can be achieved through offering leadership support and advice, mentorship, career development and solving individual needs among their employees.

1) Responses on the Use of Individualized Consideration and Organizational Performance

The lecturers were required to indicate their level of agreement on individualized consideration and its influence of performance of private universities in Kenya Table 3 shows the lecturer’s responses on individualized consideration and performance. A five-point likert scale was used: where; 1= Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree.

Table 3. Responses on Individualized Consideration and Performance of Private Universities

	N	Mean	SD
In this university, leaders spend time teaching and coaching lecturers	231	4.04	.959
Top leadership treats others as individuals rather than just as members of the organization	231	4.11	.910

Top leadership considers individuals as having different needs, abilities and aspirations from others	231	4.11	1.031
Top leadership helps others to develop their strengths in the university	231	3.94	1.106
Leaders in our organization train lecturers to enable them to achieve the company's objectives	231	3.84	1.184
Total Average	231	4.01	1.038

The study findings in Table 3 revealed that Individualized consideration deals with staff training, coaching, and mentorship programmes in the private universities which positively impact performance. The study revealed that almost half of the lecturers agreed that leaders train lecturers to enable them to achieve the company's objectives had a mean value of 3.84 meaning that majority of the lecturers agreed with the statement. The findings concur with Tshikouvhi (2021) who sought to determine the impact of training and development programmes on the perceived performance of human resource assistants at a platinum mine in South Africa, and found through a one-sample t-test, the hypothesis was accepted. Otuko et al. (2020) found there was a positive and significant effect between training needs assessment and organizational performance in Mumias Sugar Company Limited. Thus, private universities that conduct training needs assessment to guide their training content were found to perform better than those who do not.

The findings reveal that top leadership treats others as individuals rather than just as members of the organization had a mean value of 4.11 meaning that majority of the lecturers agreed with the statement. these findings concur with Okechukwu and Godday (2019) who noted that this aspect is a genuine case of leaders who give a listening ear to their subordinates and bolster them in like manner. Debating and identifying with the necessities of individual workers, making the social relationship with the subordinates, showing credible compassion, and enabling advancing capable improvement and self-development of subordinates is a segment of the exercises undertaken in this specific circumstance. However, Tahir (2019) showed that the act of individual recognition of transformational leadership have no significant impact on employee performance.

Leaders spend time teaching and coaching lecturers had a mean of 4.04 meaning that majority of the lecturers agreed with the statement and these findings concur with Trmal (2019) who posited that mentoring is the point at which a person with huge involvement with a specific field or aptitudes invests energy with a novice in that field and attempts to build up those abilities to that individual. In the end, this will prompt a superior skilled, and educated individual. Mentoring and coaching helps the individuals to understand how the goals and their needs are related to the support of the organization's mission (Rattanaborworn & Ussahawanitchakit, 2019).

The study revealed that majority of the lecturers with a mean of 3.94 agreed with the statement that top leadership helps others to develop their strengths. The findings disagree with findings of Crompton, Smyrnios and Bi (2020) who reported a relationship between employee's confidence and mentorship and further pointed out that mentorship, as an influencing factor to employee's confidence level, has no direct impact on the organizational performance and growth. Therefore, the leader provides for individuals' needs which are the requirements of growth and achievement (Osagie & Momoh, 2019). Furthermore, as was found by Veise et al., (2021), leaders' responsiveness to employees work-related needs enhanced employees' level of satisfaction with job and their level of commitment to task completion which enhanced general performance of the firm.

The study revealed that majority of the lecturers with a mean of 4.11 agreed with the statement that top leadership considers individuals as having different needs, abilities and aspirations from others and these findings support a study by Wang and Howell (2017) who argue that transformational leader focuses on group as well as individual levels. The leader aims at empowering followers to potentially develop their abilities, skills self-efficacy and respect among others. The leaders influence their followers by strengthening their interest in them. The leader's goals is to understand the followers needs, abilities, skills, and offer coaching and mentoring which helps in overcoming individual challenges. This behavior also helps the leader inspires followers achieving the institutional goal (Matthias & Eline, 2021).

The Deans of Affairs shared that they encourage imagination and creativity by allowing the employees to be free and share their innovative ideas whenever possible. They also create an environment whereby the employees can be able to reach them and other departments to air their views on certain things. They also reward creativity and imagination among employees, having a diverse workforce that ensures diverse ideas are shared across, celebrating the successes of the employees, encouraging continuous development and training, as well as providing a space for creativity.

E. Inferential Statistical Analysis

The null hypothesis: there is no significant relationship between individualized consideration and organizational performance in private universities in Nairobi City County, Kenya.

1) Correlation Analysis

Correlational analysis using Pearson’s correlation coefficient was used to test the relationship between individualized consideration and performance of private universities. The results of the correlation are presented in the Table 4.

Table 4. Correlation Analysis for Individualized Consideration and Performance of Private Universities

		Performance	Individualized Consideration
Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	.537**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	231	231
Individualized Consideration	Pearson Correlation	.537**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	231	231

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The Table 4 shows that the computed correlation of individualized consideration and performance was 0.537 (p=0.000). This indicates that performance as the dependent variable had a positive and significant relationship with individualized consideration. Therefore, this implies that as individualized consideration in transformational leadership increases, the performance of private universities in Kenya also increases. The findings concur with a study by Komakech et al. (2021) which revealed that individual consideration had a positive and significant influence on employee performance. However, the findings disagree with Juma and Ndisya’s (2019) study which found that the relationship between individualized consideration and organizational performance was negatively correlated and statistically insignificant. In addition, a study by Kimengich et al. (2020) concluded that headteachers’ individual consideration does not have a statistically significant relationship with learners’ academic performance in primary schools in Kericho County. In summary, the lecturers agreed that when individualized consideration increases, the performance of the private universities increases too.

II) Regression Analysis

Regression analysis was done to determine the relationship between the indicators of individualized consideration and performance of private universities at an alpha value of 0.05 significance level.

Table 5. Model Summary for Individualized Consideration and Organizational Performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.638	.457	.473	6.74482

a. Predictors: (Constant), Individualized Consideration

As presented in Table 5, the degree to individual consideration influences performance was statistically significant, $R^2 = 0.457$, $F(1, 229) = 13.751$, $p\text{-value} < 0.05$. This shows that 45.7% of performance can be attributed to individual consideration while the remaining 54.3% can be attributed to other factors not included in the study and the error term. Table 6 shows the regression ANOVA output. The regression ANOVA determines if the model used is the best to answer the study hypothesis.

Table 6. ANOVA Table for Individualized Consideration and Organizational Performance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	625.561	1	625.561	13.751	.000 ^b
	Residual	10417.798	229	45.493		
	Total	11043.359	230			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Individualized Consideration

As presented in Table 6, individualized consideration had a significant influence on performance, $F(1, 229) = 104.144$, $p < 0.05$. This shows that the regression model used was suitable for predicting the outcome variable on how individualized consideration influences performance. The third table 4.7 shows the regression coefficient output of individualized consideration on performance advantage. The coefficient indicates the Beta values of the parameters.

Table 7. Regression Coefficients Table for Individualized Consideration and Organizational Performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1 (Constant)	37.183	2.049			18.143	.000
Individualized Consideration	.370	.100	.537		3.708	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

As presented in Table 7, individualized consideration had a significant influence on performance ($\beta = .370$, $t = 3.708$, $p < .05$). This shows that a unit change in individual consideration will affect performance by .370. Thus, the study rejected the null hypothesis, that there is no significant relationship between individualized consideration and organizational performance in private universities in Nairobi County and accepted the alternative hypothesis that there is significant relationship between individualized consideration and organizational performance in private universities in Nairobi County.

Similar views were expressed by George (2017) which concluded that individualized consideration positively and fundamentally affected the performance of legal staff. The findings further concur with Kamotho et al. (2023) found that individualized consideration had a statistically significant relationship with organizational performance. In addition, Gaiti and Kiiru (2021) established a positive relationship between individualized consideration and performance of public universities. However, Musyoki (2022) who found that individualized consideration has a negative and significant impact on academic performance.

VII. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

A. Conclusion

Transformational leadership is a process in which leaders and followers help each other to advance to a higher level of morale and motivation, creating significant changes in the lives of people and organizations. The purpose of the study was to investigate the influence of individualized consideration style on organization performance in private universities in Nairobi City County, Kenya. The main reason was to establish how individualized consideration influences organizational performance in private universities in Nairobi City County, Kenya.

Individualized consideration was seen to be used by private universities in Nairobi County as it directly contributed to their performance. The findings from the lecturers and Deans of Academic Affairs imply that individualized consideration is very crucial in attaining performance in private universities. University administrators who are the key factors provide the most valuable leadership by improving performance and employee commitment. Therefore, the leaders should offer leadership support and advice, mentorship, career development and solving individual needs among their employees. The indicators of individualized consideration include ($\beta = .370$, $t = 3.708$, $p < .05$). the null hypothesis states that “There is no significant relationship between individualized consideration and organizational performance in private universities in Nairobi City County, Kenya” was rejected at $p < 0.05$ hence

the model was significant there is no significant influence of individualized consideration to organizational performance in private universities in Kenya.

B. Recommendations

The objective of the study was to investigate the relationship between individualized consideration and organizational performance in private universities in Nairobi City County, Kenya. Hypothesis that was tested was that there was no significant relationship between individualized consideration and organizational performance in private universities in Nairobi City County, Kenya. From the findings of the study on individualized consideration and organizational performance in private universities, the study concludes that there is a positive and significant relationship between individualized consideration and organizational performance in private universities. Observed results further indicated that individualized consideration as an element of transformational leadership was practiced in private universities in Kenya thus demonstrating a high level of relationship between individualized consideration and organizational performance in the private universities.

Therefore, the study recommends that the management of private universities ought to offer leadership support and advice to their employees, as well as helping in solving the employees' needs as this is important in improving their performance. Furthermore, they should realize that in order to realize higher performance for their institutions they need to ensure that the leaders in the institutions act as both mentors and coaches for the employees and recognize their contributions to the organization. The Deans of Academic Affairs need to attend seminars and training in transformational leadership so that they can be well-versed in transformational leadership skills, responsibilities, and characteristics. When the Deans of Academic Affairs attend these training on capacity building, they get the quality transformational leadership skills. Additionally, the leaders in private universities should empower employees by engaging them in decision making, and encouraging them to think critically if they expect to realize higher performance of their respective institutions.

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REFERENCES

1. Abagi, J. O. (2017). *Revitalizing Financing of Higher education in Kenya: Resource Utilization in Public Universities*. Accra: Association of African Universities.
2. Ahmad, F., Abbas, T., Latif, S. & Rasheed, A. (2019). Impact of Transformational Leadership on Employee Motivation in Telecommunication Sector. *Journal of Management Policies and Practices*, 2(2), 11-25.
3. Al Khajeh, E. H. (2018). Impact of Leadership Styles on Organizational Performance. *Journal of Human Resources Management Research*, 2018, Article ID: 687849.
4. Alatawi, M. A. (2022). The myth of the additive effect of the transformational leadership model. *Contemporary Management Research*, 13(1), 45-75.
5. Altbach, P. G., Reisberg, L., & Rumbley, L. E. (2019). *Trends in global higher education: Tracking an academic revolution*. UNESCO; Sense Publishers.
6. Antonakis, J., & House, R. (2019). An analysis of the full-range leadership theory: The way forward. In B. J. Avolio & F. J. Yammarino (Eds.), *Transformational and charismatic leadership: The road ahead* (pp. 3-33). Amsterdam: JAI Press.
7. Aondo, R. (2020). *Transformational leadership style, staff loyalty, internal environment and performance of chartered universities in Kenya*. Unpublished PhD thesis, Management University of Africa.

8. Avolio, B. J., & Bass, B. M. (1995). Individual consideration viewed at multiple levels of analysis: A multi-level framework for examining the diffusion of transformational leadership. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 6(2), 199–218.
9. Bass, B. M., & Riggio, R. E. (2006). *Transformational leadership* (2nd ed.). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Publishers.
10. Bass, B.M. (1985). *Leadership performance beyond expectations*. New York: Free Press.
11. Bell, M. & Omachonu, V. (2021). Quality system implementation process for business success. *International Journal of Quality and Reliability Management*, 28(7), 723 – 773
12. Birasnav M., Albufalasa M., Bader Y. (2021). The role of transformational leadership and knowledge management processes on predicting product and process innovation: an empirical study developed in Kingdom of Bahrain. *Tékhné 11*, 64–75.
13. Burns, J. M. (1978). *Leadership*. New York: Harper and Row Publishers.
14. Bush, T. (2008). *Leadership and management development*. London: SAGE Publication Ltd.
15. Bush, T. (2013). Distributed leadership: The model of choice in the 21st century. *Educational management administration & leadership*, 41(5), 543-544.
16. Chandan J.S., (2021). *Organizational Behaviour*. New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House (Pvt) Ltd
17. Chebon, S., Aruasa, W., & Chirchir, L. (2019). Effect of Inspirational Motivation and Idealized Influence on Employee Performance at Moi Teaching and Referral Hospital, Eldoret, Kenya. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*. 10(7), 14
18. Choi, T.Y., & Eboch, K. (2019). The TQM paradox: relations among TQM practices, plant performance, and customer satisfaction. *Journal of Operations Management*, 17, 59-75.
19. Cooper, D. & Schindler, P. (2014). *Business research methods* (11th edition.). Boston, MA: McGraw-Hill Higher Education.
20. Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: Choosing Among Five Designs* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
21. Crompton, B., Smyrniotis, K., & Bi, R. (2020). Measuring the influence of business coaching on fast-growth firms. *Small Enterprise Research*, 19(1), 16–31.
22. Desky H., Mukhtasar M. I., Ariesa Y., Dewi I. B. M., Fahlevi M., Nur M. (2020). Did trilogy leadership style, organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) and organizational commitment (OCO) influence financial performance? Evidence from pharmacy industries. *Systematic Reviews Journal of Pharmacy*, 11, 297–305
23. Evangelos, L & Psomas, E. (2022). The effectiveness of the ISO quality management system in service firms. *Total Quality Management and business excellence*, 24, 769-781.
24. Fotopoulos, C., Psomas, E. & Vouzas, F. (2020). Investigating total quality management practices inter-relationships in ISO:2000 certified organizations. *Total quality management & Business Excellence*, 21(5), 503-515.
25. Gaiti M. G., & Kiiru, D. (2021). Influence of transformational leadership on performance of public universities in Nyeri County, Kenya. *The Strategic Journal of Business & Change Management*, 8(1), 210 – 219.
26. Galletta, A. (2013). *Mastering the semi-structured interview and beyond: From research design to analysis and publication*. New York, USA: New York University Press.
27. Gelard P., Boroumand Z., Mohammadi A. (2019). Relationship between transformational leadership and knowledge management. *International Journal of Information, Science Management*, 67–82.
28. George, M. (2016). Transformational leadership styles and their influence on the performance of judicial staff in Kenya. *Journal of Management*, 23(3), 409- 473.
29. Hair, J., Money, A., Page, M. and Samouel, P. (2006). *Research Methods for Business*. London: Routledge.
30. Hildebrand, D., & Ott, V. (2011). *Qualitative Research in Information Systems*. (Eds.) London: Sage
31. Indrawan I., Evanirosa A. R., Indra R. H. M., & Sumartiningih S. (2020). Develop model of transactional, transformational, democratic and autocratic leadership style for Indonesian school performance in education 4.0 era. *Systematic Reviews Journal of Pharmacy*, 11, 409–419.

32. Juma, D. O., & Ndisya, S. N. (2019). Influence of Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance. A Case Study of Safaricom Limited. *Strategic Journal of Business & Change Management*, 3(2), 85-141.
33. Kadiyono A. L., Sulistiobudi R. A., Haris I., Wahab M. K. A., Ramdani I., Purwanto A., Mufid, A., Muqtada, M., Nuryansah, G., Ficayuma, L., Fahlevi, M., & Sumartiningshi, S. (2020). Develop leadership style model for Indonesian teachers' performance in education 4.0 era. *Systematic Reviews Journal of Pharmacy*, 11, 363–373.
34. Kamotho, J., Koome, P., & Kithinji, J. (2023). Effects of Individualized Consideration on Organizational Performance: A Case of Parishes Within the All-Saints' Cathedral Diocese Nairobi, Kenya. *Impact: Journal of Transformation*, 6(1), 52-67.
35. Kao, S. F., & Tsai, C. Y. (2019). Transformational leadership and athlete satisfaction: The mediating role of coaching competency. *Journal of Applied Sport Psychology*, 28(4), 469-482.
36. Karamat, A. U. (2018). Impact of Organizational Leadership on Organizational Performance. A case Study of D & R Cambric Communication. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 22(5), 221-229.
37. Kimengich, J., Ngeno, V., & Kaptingei, S. (2020). Relationship between the Head Teacher's Individualized Consideration and Learners' Academic Performance in Primary Schools in Kericho County, Kenya. *The International Journal of Humanities & Social Studies*, 8(11), 109-116.
38. Kinara, K. R., Ondari, J., Omari, S., Akuku, C. (2023) Influence of individualized consideration dimension on organizational performance of the South Eastern Kenya Economic Bloc (SEKEB) counties. The moderating role of innovation. *International Academic Journal of Human Resource and Business Administration*, 4(2), 418-441.
39. Kirkbride, G. C. (2006). Impact of perceived leadership styles on work outcomes: case of building professionals. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 131(4), 413-422.
40. Komakech, E., Obici, G & Mwesigwa, D., (2021). Intellectual Stimulation and Employee Performance. Reflections on Middle-level Health Care Workers in Lira District Uganda. *International Journal of Thesis Projects and Dissertation (UTPD)*, 9 (12), 46-57.
41. Kothari, C. R. (2013). *Research methodology: Methods and techniques* (2nd Ed). New Delhi, India: New Age International (P) Ltd. Publishers.
42. Lucas, M., & Donnellan, F. (2012). Design and analysis in dissemination and implementation research. Purposeful Sampling for Qualitative Data Collection and Analysis in Mixed Method Implementation Research. *Springer Science and Business Media New York*, 42(5), 533-44.
43. Lumbasi, G. W., K' Aol, G. O., and Ouma, C. A. (2016). The Effect of Achievement Oriented leadership Style on the Performance of COYA Senior Managers in Kenya. *International Journal of Novel Research in Marketing Management and Economics*, 3(2), 118-125.
44. Mansour, D., Mun, P., Farhana, S., Nasuha, W., Tarmizi, W. (2017). Influence of Transformation Leadership Style on Employee Engagement among Generation Y. *International Journal of Social, Behavioral, Educational, Economic, Business and Industrial Engineering*, 11(1), 161-167.
45. Matthias, A., & Eline, O. (2016). Embracing transformational leadership: Team values and the impact of leader behavior on team performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 92(4), 1020-1030
46. Mbirithi, D. M. (2019). *Management challenges facing Kenya's public universities and implications for quality of education*. Kenyatta University. Unpublished Thesis.
47. Michieka, R. W. (2017). *Trails in Academic and Administrative Leadership in Kenya*. Nairobi: CODESRIA.
48. Milelu, V. (2019). *Effects of transformational leadership on organizational performance within public universities in Kenya: A case of Kenyatta University*. (Masters' thesis), United States International University – Africa.
49. Mwaniki, F. N., Muhoho, J., & Njoroge, J. (2020). Influence of individualized transformational leadership on organizational performance of selected SACCO's in Kiambu Town. *The Strategic Journal of Business & Change Management*, 7(3), 960 – 972.
50. Mwove, P. (2023). *Principals' leadership styles influencing students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Mwala Sub-County, Machakos County*. (Master's thesis), South Eastern Kenya University.

51. Najeeb, A. (2019). The balance on the balanced scorecard a critical analysis of some of its assumptions. *Management Accounting Research*, 11(1), 65-88.
52. Northouse, P. G. (2014). *Leadership: theory and practice* (7th ed.). London, UK: Sage Publications.
53. Ogolla, J. (2020). *Transformational leadership, strategic agility and performance of state corporations in Kenya*. (Doctorate dissertation), Kenya Methodist University.
54. Ogolla, K., Bolo, A., & Muchemi, M. (2019). Determinants of strategic forces that shape competition in handcraft industry in Kenya. *Business Administration and Management Prime Journal*, 2 (2), 36-49
55. Okechukwu & Godday, R. L. (2019). Impact of Coaching and Mentoring in the Nigerian Liquefied Natural Gas Company Limited, Bonny. *European Journal of Sustainable Development*, 4(1), 85-100.
56. Ondari, J.N., Were, S., & Rotich, J. (2018). Effect of individual consideration on organizational performance of state corporations in Kenya. *Journal of Management*, 5(1), 210 – 246.
57. Orodho, A.J., Khatete, I., & Mugiraneza, J.P. (2016). *Concise Statistics: An illustrative approach to problem-solving*. Nairobi: Kanezja Publisher.
58. Orodho, J. A. 2017 *Elements of education and social science research methods*. Maseno: Kanezja Publishers.
59. Ortagus, J. C., Kelchen, R., Rosinger, K., & Voorhees, N. (2020). Performance-based funding in American higher education: A systematic synthesis of the intended and unintended consequences. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 42(4), 520-550.
60. Osagie, R.O & Momoh, U, (2019). Principals' Leadership and Student Performance in Senior Secondary Schools in Edo State, Nigeria. *Educational Planning*, 23(3), 17-28.
61. Prasad, B., & Junni, P. (2021). CEO transformational and transactional leadership and organizational innovation. *Management Decision*, 2(1), 66-81
62. Rattanaborworn, J., & Ussahawanitchakit, P (2019). Transformational leadership and firm performance: empirical evidence from instant foods and convenience foods businesses in Thailand. *The Business and Management Review*, 7(1), 12-23.
63. Sarros, J.C., Cooper, B., & Santora, J.C. (2012). Building a Climate for Innovation Through Transformational Leadership and Organizational Culture. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 15, 145 - 158.
64. Shadraconis, E. (2013). Delegation and employee work outcomes: An examination of the cultural context of mediating processes in China. *Academy of Management Journal*, 50(1), 226-236.
65. Shikokoti, H., Okoth, U., & Chepkonga, S. (2023). Influence of Principals' Involvement of Teachers in Decision Making on Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Public Secondary Schools in Kakamega County, Kenya. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 14(20), 28-35.
66. Silva, D. A. C. S., & Mendis, B. A. K. M. (2019). Male vs female leaders: Analysis of transformational, transactional & laissez-faire women leadership styles. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 9(9), 19-26.
67. Söderlind, J., & Geschwind, L. (2019). Making sense of academic work: The influence of performance measurement in Swedish universities. *Policy Reviews in Higher Education*, 3(1), 75-93.
68. Tahir, H. (2019). Leadership style and Organizational Performance: A Comparative study between Transformational and Transactional Leadership styles. *IBT Journal of Business Studies* 11(2), 257-274.
69. Trmal, S. A. (2019). The Effect of Transformational Leadership in Achieving High-Performance Workforce That Exceeds Organizational Expectations. A Study from a Global and Islamic Perspective. *Global Business and Management Research*, 7(2), 88-94.
70. Tshikouvhi, C. (2021). Institutionalization of organizational ethics through transformational leadership. *Journal of business ethics*. 14(10), 829 –839
71. Veiseh, S., Mohammadi, E., Pirzadian, M. & Sharafi, V. (2021). The Relation between Transformational Leadership and Organizational Culture: Case study: Medical school of Ilam. *Journal of Business Studies Quarterly*, 5(3), 113-121.
72. Waiganjo, E., Mukulu, E., & Kahiri, J. (2017). Relationship between Strategic Human Resource Management and Firm Performance of Kenya's Corporate Organizations. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 2(1), 63- 68.

73. Wang, H., & Howell, J. (2017). Exploring the dual-level effects of transformational leadership on followers. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 95(6), 1134-1144.
74. Wanzala, W. (2019). Quest for Quality and Relevant Higher Education, Training and Learning in Kenya: an Overview. *Education Journal*, 2(2), 36-49
75. Yukl, G. (2009). Leading organizational learning: Reflections on theory and research. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 20(1), 49–53.

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